

A Study on the economic analysis of direction of India's exports

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ABSTRACT

A nation's exports are crucial to the expansion of its economy. The growth of this industry is a good sign of a nation's economic health. It promotes other areas of the Indian economy as well as productivity growth and job creation. The current study examine the growth trends of India's exports to different regional groups and the analysis is based on time series secondary data that was gathered from a variety of government agencies, including the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics, and Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy. Excel and SPSS were used to conduct the analysis. Tables and other descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. The direction of India's exports have been analysed for trends and growth rates using a linear model. Studying the trends and growth rate of India's exports to various regional groups from 1991–1992 to 2016–17 involved using the semi log model and compound growth rate.

Keywords: *India's Exports, Linear Model, Semi Log Model.*

INTRODUCTION

Any economy must have foreign commerce, and over the past 69 years, that role has grown in the global economy. (1999, Paul Krugman). It is extremely important for a country's economic development as it has contributed significantly to economic growth and the general economic well-being of the populace. The movement of commodities and services into and out of a nation's foreign commerce results in the inflow and outflow of foreign currency from one nation to another. No nation in the world has the necessary infrastructure for the efficient production of all the commodities and services that its citizens use. This suggests that no nation is self-

sufficient in the sense of being able to generate all the products it requires. As a result, there is a demand for trade between people. Through international trade, economies of scale and worldwide specialization—which are also the results of global scientific and technological advancement—would be more readily available (Agarwal, 1975). More items are required by developing nations to feed their constantly expanding populations. Exports may be the fastest-growing industry. The implication is clear: a country's domestic industrial activity would be stimulated by higher earnings from its commodities' increased marketability on the global market. As a result, there are numerous positive effects, including better resource usage, more employment prospects, increased foreign exchange, etc. Thus, it was believed that foreign trade would significantly contribute to a nation's development; as a result, it is now regarded as an engine of growth as well as a tool for increasing productivity. International commerce is now a crucial component of development strategy and may be a powerful tool for boosting an economy's productivity, creating jobs, and reducing poverty. All developed and developing economies depend heavily on export for their economic growth. The expansion of international organisations like the WTO, UNCTAD, ASEAN, and others has accelerated global trade growth. Studying the nations from which imports come and to which exports go is known as trade direction. The trends and growth rates of India's exports from 1991–1992 to 2016–2017 are reviewed in this study.

SIGNIFICANCE FOR THE STUDY

Any nation's economic growth is fueled by international trade. In the years since India's economy was liberalised in 1991, both its exports and imports have skyrocketed. However, the value of imports continues to exceed the value of exports. Therefore, it is necessary to accelerate India's growth rate. Export is crucial for economic growth since it results in the acquisition of foreign currency, which supports economic expansion. More economic expansion results in a more prosperous country. The report sheds light on the patterns and rate of change of India's exports. Currently, global trade is a crucial component of the development strategy and can be a useful tool for reducing poverty by increasing output, creating jobs, earning foreign currency, developing the financial sector, mobilising domestic resources, and maximising saving so that the economic benefits spread to a larger population (Mathanraj.T 2019). Adopting appropriate measures to promote trade would be beneficial for the policymaker. The researcher who is just starting out in the subject of international economics would also benefit from this study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the patterns and rates of change in the direction of India's exports from 1991–1992 to 2016–17
- To investigate the growth trends of India's exports to various regional groups.
- To determine the countries that India exports to, including those in SAARC, OECD, OPEC, and Africa.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current analysis is based on time series secondary data that was gathered from a variety of government agencies, including the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics, and Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy. Excel and SPSS were used to conduct the analysis. Tables and other descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. Similar attempts are made to show the gathered data in this section through line graphs and bar diagrams. The direction of India's exports have been analysed for trends and growth rates using a linear model. Studying the trends and growth rate of India's exports to various regional groups from 1991–1992 to 2016–17 involved using the semi log model and compound growth rate.

TOOLS OF USED THE STUDY

The researcher had analyzed the collected data with the basic objectives of the study in mind. Some of the tools involved in the study include

1. Linear model
2. Semi-log Model and compound growth rate
3. 'T' test

LINEAR MODEL

Further the researcher has used percentage and the simple linear growth rate model. The linear growth rate model

$$Y = a + b_t$$

Where, Y - Dependent variable, T – Time, 'a' and 'b' are the parameters. The linear growth rate is obtained from the 'b' value.

SEMI LOG MODEL AND COMPOUND GROWTH RATE

Further the researcher has used the Semi log model, in order to compute the Instantaneous Growth Rate and the Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) the Semi-log is used and was computed using the following models.

If Y_t = Variable at time t and Y₀ = initial year value of the variable, simple compounding is explained as

$$\log Y = a + b_t$$

$$CGR = (\text{Anti log } b - 1)100$$

‘T’TEST

$$b_1 - b_2$$

$$t = \frac{b_1 - b_2}{\sqrt{(S.E. b_1)^2 + (S.E. b_2)^2}}$$

$$\sqrt{(S.E. b_1)^2 + (S.E. b_2)^2}$$

Here b_1 represented the slope coefficient obtained in the regression model, which was estimated for the study period and b_2 was the slope coefficient obtained in the regression model estimated for the study period S.E. is the standard error.

DIRECTION OF INDIA’S EXPORTS

The direction of exports is determined by the numerous regional organisations and India's export of certain commodities. This chapter looks at the different groups that comprise India's exports, including OPEC (Oil Producing and Exporting Countries), OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development), European Union (EU), Asia and Oceania, North America, Developing Countries, SAARC (South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation), other Asian Developing Countries, and African Countries.

TABLE NO.1.1 INDIA’S EXPORT TO VARIOUS REGIONAL GROUPS FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17(US\$ Million)

Countries	1991- 92	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16	2016-17
OPEC Countries	1561.8	3079	4850	15242.2	47812.1	46236	45309.9
OECD Countries	10337	17705.1	23473.6	45836.9	83448.3	101102.5	104930.6
Eastern Europe	1952.7	1340	1317.8	1980.4	2715.9	2438.5	2820.2
Developing Countries	3587.1	9198.4	13012.6	39736.4	101730	109171	120216.2

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S)

According to Table No.1.1, India's exports to developing nations climbed from \$3,587.1 million in 1991–1992, to \$39,736.4 million in 2005–2006, and to \$1,20,216.2 million in 2016–17. India's exports to OECD nations have grown from \$10,337 million in 1991–1992, \$45836.9 million in 2005–2006, and \$1, 04,930.6 million in 2016–17. India's OPEC exports climbed from \$1,561.8 million in 1991–1992 to \$47812.1 million in 2010–2011 before declining to \$45,309.9 million in 2016–17. India's exports to Eastern Europe have decreased over the years, from \$1952.7 million in 1991–1992, to \$1,317.8 million in 2000–2001, to \$2715.9 million in 2010–2011, and lastly to \$2,820.2 million in 2016–2017.

TABLE NO.1.2. TREND AND GROWTH RATE OF INDIA’S EXPORT TO VARIOUS REGIONAL GROUP DURING 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Variable	Linear Model				Semi log Model				CGR
	a	B	t	R ²	a	b	t	R ²	
OPEC	26822.60 (37671.74)	4912.79 (2439.33)	2.014	0.145	7.047 (0.236)	0.175 (0.015)	11.489	0.846	19.2
OECD Countries	-11309.37 (4807.47)	4512.29 (311.29)	14.495	0.897	9.125 (0.057)	0.103 (0.004)	28.047	0.970	10.9
Eastern Europe	665.668 (214.82)	97.663 (13.910)	7.021	0.659	6.811 (0.100)	0.051 (0.006)	7.781	0.704	5.2
Developing Countries	29190.83 (7873.47)	5953.30 (509.82)	11.677	0.850	8.116 (0.097)	0.157 (0.006)	24.894	0.963	17.0

Source: Calculated by the researcher (Figures in bracket indicate Standard Error)

The t values of the trend co-efficient were found to be statistically significant at the 1% level, according to Table No. 1.2. The R2 values were likewise determined to be acceptable. Developing Nations had the highest yearly average export value of US \$5953.30 million among the various regional groupings of countries that India exported to. With an average annual export value of US \$4912.79 million, OPEC ranked second. The OECD, which had an average annual export value of \$4512.29 million USD, came in third, while Eastern Europe had the lowest average annual export value at US\$97.66 million USD. Regarding the growth rates of the exports of the major regional exporting countries, OPEC had the highest growth rate, at 17.5% annually, while developing countries had the second-highest growth rate, at 15.7% annually. OECD, which has an export growth rate of 10.3% annually, took third position. The lowest export growth rates were recorded in Eastern Europe which has 5.1 per cent per annum. When it came to the

compound growth rate of exports, OPEC had the highest rate (19.2% annually), and Eastern Europe had the lowest rate (5.2% annually).

TABLE NO.1.3. INDIA’S EXPORT TO OPEC COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17(US\$ Million)

Countries	1991-92	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16	2016-17
Iran	122.5	155.0	227.0	1188.3	2488.3	2776.8	2392.3
Iraq	0.0	0.6	84.0	155.9	674.9	999.8	1115.7
Kuwait	52.3	135.5	199.1	513.7	1854.0	1245.4	1494.2
Saudi Arabia	351.3	482.3	822.9	1809.8	4674.1	6385.7	5136.3
UAE	738.5	1428.3	2597.5	8591.8	33770.3	30295.5	31233.6
Eastern Europe	1952.7	1340.0	1317.8	1980.4	2715.9	2438.5	2820.2
Russia	1640.0	1045.0	889.0	733.1	1691.4	1593.3	1931.7
OPEC	1561.8	3079	4850.0	15242.2	47812.1	46236.0	45309.9

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics

The Table No.1.3 reveals among the OPEC countries, UAE went up from \$738.5 million US dollar in 1991-92 to \$8,591.8 million US dollar in 2005-06 and \$31,233.6 million US dollar in 2016-17. India’s export to Saudi Arabia improved from \$351.3 million US dollar in 1991-92 then gradually increased to \$6,385.7 million US dollar in 2015-16 and finally fell down to \$5,136.3 million US dollar in 2016-17. India’s export to Iran increased from \$1, 22.5 million US dollar in 1991-92 to \$1,188.3 million US dollar in 2005-06 and \$2,392.3 million US dollar in 2016-17. India’s export to Iraq increased from \$0.0 million US dollar in 1991-92 to \$155.9 million US dollar in 2005-06 and it reached to \$1,115.7 million US dollar in 2016-17.

TABLE NO.1.4. TREND AND GROWTH RATE OF INDIA’S EXPORT TO OPEC COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Variable	Linear Model				Semi log Model				CGR
	a	B	t	R ²	a	B	t	R ²	
OPEC	26822.60 (37671.74)	4912.795 (2439.33)	2.014	0.145	7.047 (0.236)	0.175 (0.015)	11.489	0.846	19.2

Iran	-783.142 (268.996)	161.109 (17.418)	9.250	0.781	4.308 (0.168)	0.166 (0.11)	15.219	0.906	18.0
Iraq	-287.878 (76.272)	46.819 (4.939)	9.480	0.888	-	-	-	-	-
Kuwait	-225.571 (94.298)	59.654 (6.106)	9.770	0.799	4.199 (0.099)	0.128 (0.006)	19.939	0.943	13.6
Saudi Arabia	-1895.44 (816.355)	374.292 (52.861)	7.081	0.676	5.504 (0.128)	0.144 (0.0089)	17.415	0.927	15.5
UAE	-7829.82 (11263.067)	1974.076 (729.310)	2.707	0.234	6.331 (0.245)	0.184 (0.016)	11.629	0.849	20.2
Eastern Europe	665.668 (214.824)	97.663 (13.910)	7.021	0.673	6.811 (0.100)	0.006 (0.100)	7.781	0.716	5.2
Russia	528.986 (164.215)	46.430 (10.633)	4.366	0.443	6.464 (0.131)	0.037 (0.009)	4.327	0.438	3.7

Source: Calculated by the researcher (Figures in bracket indicate Standard Error)

As seen in Table No.1.4, the trend co-t efficient's values were determined to be statistically significant at the 1% level. The R2 values were likewise determined to be acceptable. UAE had the highest yearly average export value of US \$1,974.07 million among India's export destinations in OPEC. With an average annual export value of US \$374.29 million, Saudi Arabia ranked second. Iran, which had an average annual export value of US \$161.10 million, was ranked third, followed by Kuwait (US \$59.65 million) in that order. Iraq's average annual export value was the lowest at US \$ 46.81 million. When it comes to the OPEC nations' export growth rates, the UAE has the highest growth rate (18.4% per year), Iran had the second-highest growth rate (16.6% per year), and Saudi Arabia came in third with a growth rate of 14.4% per year. With an annual growth rate of 12.8%, Kuwait had the lowest export growth rate. UAE had the highest compound growth rate for exports, with an annual growth rate of 20,2%. With a compound growth rate of 13.6% annually, Kuwait had the lowest rate.

TABLE NO.1.5. INDIA’S EXPORT TO OECD COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17(US\$ Million)

Countries	1991-92	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16	2016-17
OECD Countries	10337	17705	23473	45836	83448	101102	104930
European Union	4826	8708	10410	22385	46123	44726	47599
North America	3109	5825	9961	18374	26634	42452	44322
Asia and Oceania	1878	2651	2263	3444	6991	8238	7128
Other OECD	522	519	837	1632	3638	5685	5880

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics

According to Table No.1.5, the European Union increased from 1991–1992 to 2016–2017, going from \$4,826 million in 1991–1992 to \$22,385 million in 2005–2006 and \$47,599 million in 2016–2017. India's exports to North America increased rapidly throughout the years, rising from \$3,109 million in 1991–1992 to \$26,634 million in 2010–11 and \$44,322 million in 2016–17. From \$1,878 million in 1991–1992, to \$3,444 million in 2005–2006, and finally to \$7,128 million in 2016–17, India's exports to Asia and Oceania have expanded. India's exports to other members of the OECD increased from \$522 million in 1991–1992, to \$5,685 million in 2015–2016, and finally to \$5880 million in 2016–17.

TABLE 1.6. TREND AND GROWTH RATE OF INDIA’S EXPORT TO OECD COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Variable	Linear Model				Semi log Model				CGR
	A	B	t	R ²	a	B	t	R ²	
OECD Countries	11309.371 (4807.472)	4512.290 (311.295)	14.495	0.897	9.125 (0.057)	0.103 (0.004)	28.047	0.970	10.9
European Union	-5483.314 (2545.631)	2199.012 (164.836)	13.341	0.881	8.350 (0.078)	0.106 (0.005)	20.951	0.948	11.2
North America	-4892.714 (1830.053)	1752.610 (118.500)	14.790	0.901	8.081 (0.041)	0.108 (0.003)	40.476	0.986	11.4

Asia and Oceania	152.474 (513.962)	308.925 (33.280)	9.283	0.782	7.245 (0.093)	0.071 (0.006)	11.691	0.851	7.3
Other OECD	-1084.526 (397.264)	251.477 (25.724)	9.776	0.799	5.730 (0.111)	0.118 (0.007)	16.398	0.918	12.5

Source: Calculated by the researcher (Figures in bracket indicate Standard Error)

The trend co-t efficient's values were found to be statistically significant at the 1% level, as shown in Table 1.6. The R2 values were likewise determined to be acceptable. European Union had the greatest annual average export value of US \$2,199.01 million per year among India's exports to OECD nations; North America had the second-highest annual average export value of US \$1,752.61 million per annum. Asia and Oceania, with an average annual export value of US \$308.92 million, claimed third place. The average export value for non-OECD countries was the lowest at US \$251.47 million annually. In terms of the OECD countries' export growth rates, the non-OECD region had the highest growth rate (11.8%), North America had the second-highest growth rate (10.8%%), and the European Union came in third with a growth rate of 10.6% annually. Asia and Oceania had the lowest export growth rate, with an annual growth rate of 7.1%. Asia and Oceania had the lowest compound growth rate of exports at 7.3% per year, while other OECD countries had the highest compound growth rate of exports at 12.5% per year.

TABLE 1.7 INDIA’S EXPORT TO EUROPEAN UNION FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17(US\$ Million)

Countries	1991-92	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16	2016-17
Belgium	666	1120	1470	2871	5782	5091	5664
France	425	747	1020	2079	5199	4635	5375
Germany	1269	1977	1907	3586	6745	7110	7243
Italy	580	1014	1308	2519	4543	4224	4944
Netherlands	372	769	880	2474	7674	4731	5057
UK	1138	2010	2298	5059	7307	8863	8576
E Union	4826	8708	10410	22385	46123	44726	47599

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics

According to Table No.1.7, exports to the UK climbed from \$1,138 million in 1991–1992, \$5,059 million in 2005–2006, and \$8,576 million in 2016–17. India's exports to Germany

increased from \$1,269 million in 1991–1992, to \$6,745 million in 2010–2011, and then to \$7,243 million in 2016–2017. India's exports to Belgium increased quickly from \$666 million in 1991–1992, to \$5,091 million in 2016, to \$5,664 million in 2017–18. India's exports to Italy increased from \$580 million in 1991–1992, \$1,308 million in 2003–2004, and \$4, 944 million in 2016–2017.

TABLE 1.8 TREND AND GROWTH RATE OF INDIA’S EXPORT TO EUROPEAN UNION FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Variable	Linear Model				Semi log Model				CGR
	a	B	t	R ²	A	b	t	R ²	
Belgium	-419.144 (318.495)	252.965 (20.623)	12.266	0.862	6.418 (0.075)	0.098 (0.005)	20.235	0.945	10.3
France	-719.506 (265.566)	225.110 (17.196)	13.091	0.877	5.876 (0.067)	0.113 (0.004)	26.114	0.966	12.0
Germany	-114.197 (368.617)	299.874 (23.869)	12.563	0.868	6.982 (0.078)	0.081 (0.005)	16.101	0.915	8.5
Italy	-286.149 (213.537)	209.989 (13.827)	15.187	0.906	6.279 (0.075)	0.097 (0.005)	20.078	0.944	10.2
Netherlands	-1370.601 (720.071)	346.119 (46.626)	7.423	0.697	5.750 (0.153)	0.135 (0.010)	13.615	0.885	14.4
UK	-478.359 (374.829)	378.575 (24.271)	15.598	0.910	6.955 (0.067)	0.092 (0.004)	21.273	0.950	9.7
E Union	-5483.314 (2545.631)	2199.012 (164.836)	13.341	0.881	8.350 (0.078)	0.106 (0.005)	20.951	0.948	11.2

Source: Calculated by the researcher (Figures in bracket indicate Standard Error)

It is clear from Table No. 1.8 above that the trend co-t efficient's values were determined to be statistically significant at the 1% level. The R2 values were likewise determined to be acceptable. UK had the highest yearly average export value of US \$378.57 million among India's export destinations in the EU. With an average export value of US \$ 346.11 million annually, the

Netherlands ranked second. Germany, with an average yearly export value of US \$299.87 million, came in third, ahead of Belgium (\$252.96 million) and France (\$225.11 million) annually. The average annual export value from Italy was the lowest at US\$209.98 million. In terms of the growth rate of exports from nations that are members of the European Union, the Netherlands ranked first with a growth rate of 13.5% per year, followed by France with a growth rate of 11.3% per year, and Belgium with a growth rate of 9.8% per year. With an annual growth rate of 8.1%, Germany had the lowest export growth rate. The Netherlands had the highest compound growth rate for exports, with an annual growth rate of 14.4%. With an annual compound growth rate of 8.5%, Germany had the lowest rate.

TABLE 1.9 INDIA’S EXPORT TO DEVELOPING COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Countries	1991-92	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16	2016-17
Asian Countries	3016.4	7307.8	10037.9	30981.2	75759.2	76497.5	88559.8
Other Asian Developing Countries	2394.9	5587.2	8109.4	25433.5	64122.8	58611	69555.7
African Countries	441.3	1512.7	1956.4	5699	15880.4	21378.4	19915.7
Latin American Countries	129.5	377.9	1018.2	3056.2	10090.1	11295	11740.6
Developing Countries	3587.1	9198.4	13012.6	39736.4	101730	109171	120216

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics

According to Table No. 1.9, Asia's share of global development aid climbed from \$3016.4 million in 1991–1992 to \$30,981.2 million in 2005–06 and \$88559.8 million in 2016–17. From \$2,394.9 million US dollars in 1991–1992, to \$64,122.8 million US dollars in 2010–2011, to \$58,611 million US dollars in 2015–2016, to \$69,555.7 million US dollars in 2016–17, India's export to other Asian Developing Countries increased rapidly. India's exports to Africa increased from \$441.3 million in 1991–1992, \$5,699 million in 2005–2006, and \$19,915.7 million in 2016–17. India's exports to countries in Latin America increased from \$129.5 million in 1991–1992, to \$1,09,171 million in 2015–2016, and then to \$1,20,216 million in 2016–17.

TABLE 1.10. TREND AND GROWTH RATE OF INDIA’S EXPORT TO DEVELOPING COUNTRIES FROM 1991-92 TO 2016-17

Variable	Linear Model				Semi log Model				CGR
	a	B	T	R ²	a	b	t	R ²	
Developing Countries	77073.99 (32292.60)	8483.43 (1553.37)	5.461	0.749	9.301 (0.370)	0.103 (0.018)	5.769	0.769	10.8
Asia Countries	47106.91 (22761.36)	5127.87 (1094.89)	5.231	0.732	9.151 (0.356)	0.095 (0.017)	5.542	0.754	10.0
Other Asian Developing Countries	31613.28 (21752.84)	4348.06 (1046.38)	4.155	0.633	9.065 (0.399)	0.089 (0.019)	4.652	0.684	9.3
Africa Countries	18881.35 (6897.29)	1754.65 (331.782)	5.289	0.737	7.164 (0.435)	0.121 (0.021)	5.781	0.770	12.9
Latin American Countries	11336.66 (4605.65)	1020.89 (221.54)	4.608	0.680	6.335 (0.495)	0.132 (0.024)	5.548	0.755	14.1

Source: Calculated by the researcher (Figures in bracket indicate Standard Error)

It is clear from Table No. 1.10 above that the trend co-efficient's values were determined to be statistically significant at the 1% level. The R2 values were likewise determined to be acceptable. Asia had the greatest yearly average export value of US \$5,127.87 million among India's exports to developing nations. With an average annual export value of US \$4,348.06 million, other Asian countries came in second. Africa, with an average annual export value of US \$1,754.65 million, claimed the third place. Latin American nations' average annual export value was the lowest at US \$1,020.89 million. Regarding the growth rate of exports from emerging nations, Latin America had the highest growth rate at 13.2% per year, followed by Africa at 12.1% per year and Asia at 9.5% per year. With an annual growth rate of 8.9%, Other Asian Countries had the lowest export growth rate. In terms of the compound growth rate of exports, Latin America had the greatest rate, at 14.1% annually. The lowest compound growth rate was 8.9% per year for other Asian countries.

CONCLUSION

Export is essential for economic expansion since it generates precious foreign exchange that promotes economic expansion. More economic expansion results in a more prosperous country. Since independence, exports have changed significantly. It is significant because of how it affects the stability of the Indian economy and internal trade. According to a study on the growth rates of exports from several regional exporting groupings, OPEC had the highest growth rate at 17.5% annually. The region with the lowest export growth rates was Eastern Europe, at 5.1% annually. When it comes to India's exports to OPEC nations, the UAE has the highest growth rate (18.4% annually), while Kuwait has the lowest growth rate (12.8% annually). Netherlands had the highest growth rate of 13.5 percent annually for exports from India to the European Union, while Germany had the lowest growth rate of 8.1 percent annually. Australia had the highest growth rate among the exporting nations to Asia and Oceania, at 11.4% annually. Japan, with a yearly growth rate of 5.6%, has the lowest export growth rate. In terms of India's exports to North American nations, the USA had the highest growth rate at 10.8% annually. Canada, with a growth rate of 10.3% annually, had the lowest export growth rate. Latin America, where India's exports to developing nations are concerned, had the highest growth rate of 13.2% per year, while Other Asian Countries had the lowest growth rate of 8.9% per year. Bhutan had the highest growth rate of 18.5% per year in terms of Indian exports to SAARC countries, while Pakistan had the lowest growth rate at 6.1% per year. In terms of India's exports to other developing Asian nations, Malaysia had the highest growth rate (11.9%) per year, while China had the lowest growth rate (3.2%) each year. Tanzania had the highest growth rate among the African exporting nations, with an annual growth rate of 19.7%; South Africa had the lowest growth rate, with an annual growth rate of 9.1%. Finally, exporters should benefit from the "Make in India" programme launched by the Indian Prime Minister. The importance of research and development must be stressed. To reduce the trade deficit and make India a successful and productive country, the best use possible must be made of all available programmes and resources. Therefore, measures that enhance and reinforce the agriculture sector's performance in the future must be implemented in order to improve the performance of the export sector.

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